

Women Crime Increase in South Solapur Taluka of Solapur District: A Geographical Analysis

Miss. Hotkar R. G.¹ & Prof. Dr. Nagnath Ishwar Dhayagode²

¹Research Student, Walchand College of Arts and Science, (Autonomous) Solapur.

²Head, Department of Geography, Walchand College of Arts and Science, (Autonomous) Solapur.

Corresponding Author – M. D. Miss. Hotkar R. G.

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Abstract:

Human geography is the synthetic study of relationship between human societies and earth's surface (Friedrich Ratzel). The study of the interrelationships between people, place and environment and how these vary spatially and temporally across and between locations. Human geography is related to the demographic characteristics of region. Crime is major issues which are related to population therefore attempt here is to made the study of crime. Violence against women is defined as any act of “gender-based violence that results in or is likely to result in physical, sexual or psychological harm or suffering to women, including threats of acts such as coercion or arbitrary deprivation of liberty, whether occurring in public or in private life.”¹ Its dimensions include physical, sexual, psychological/emotional and economic violence occurring in the family and general community or such violence perpetrated or condoned by the State. Violence against women includes domestic violence, child marriage, forced pregnancy, “honour” crimes, female genital mutilation, femicide, sexual and other violence perpetrated by someone other than an intimate partner (also referred to as non-partner violence), sexual harassment (in the workplace, other institutions and in public spaces), trafficking in women and violence in conflict situations.

Present study data shows the crime against women increase in South Solapur taluka of Solapur district.

Keywords: Women Crime.

Introduction:

The Geography of Crime cannot have a separate existence from criminology. It is an approach for evolving theoretical basic and conceptual positions for research in the area. Criminology (a field of study, the existence of which has covered two centuries) has the plurality of disciplines wherein sociologists and psychologist have made substantial contributions. Some how geography has featured minimally in this plurality and is definitively worthy of more explicit attention (Herbert, 1982).

Violence against women is defined as any act of “gender-based violence that results in or is likely to result in physical, sexual or psychological harm or suffering to women, including threats of acts such as coercion or arbitrary deprivation of liberty, whether occurring in public or in private life.”¹ Its dimensions include physical, sexual, psychological/emotional and economic violence occurring in the family and general community or such violence perpetrated or condoned by the State. Violence against women includes domestic violence, child marriage, forced pregnancy, “honour” crimes, female genital mutilation, femicide, sexual and

other violence perpetrated by someone other than an intimate partner (also referred to as non-partner violence), sexual harassment (in the workplace, other institutions and in public spaces), trafficking in women and violence in conflict situations. United Nations General Assembly, 1993. In all societies, to varying degrees, women and girls are subjected to physical, sexual and psychological abuse that cuts across lines of income, class and culture.² Such violence is recognized as a violation of human rights and a form of discrimination against women, reflecting the pervasive imbalance of power between women and men. Violence against women is found in all countries to varying degrees. A number of factors can increase the risk of violence against women and girls. These include: witnessing or experiencing violence in childhood, low levels of education, limited economic opportunities, substance abuse, attitudes that tolerate violence, and limited legislative frameworks for preventing and responding to violence. A number of initiatives have attempted to assess the scale of the problem at the international, regional and national levels. At the international level, WHO estimates that over a third (35 per cent) of women worldwide have experienced physical and/or sexual violence by an intimate partner or sexual violence by a non-partner at some point in their lives.

In India, a crime against a woman is reported every three minutes, with a rape occurring every 29 minutes, according to a 2021 report. Domestic violence is particularly prevalent, with an estimated 70% of women in India experiencing it. The National Crime Records Bureau data indicates a significant increase in reported crimes against women from 2011 to 2021.

An attempt has been made to study Women crime increases in South Solapur taluka of Solapur district.

Types Of Women Crime:

Rape, homicide for dowry, dowry deaths or their attempts, torture- both mental and physical, assault on women with intent to outrage her modesty, kidnapping and abduction and cases under Dowry Prohibition Act are the major crimes contributing more than 99 *per cent* of the incidence of crimes against women in the State.

1. Rape
2. Dowry Death
3. Kidnapping
4. Trafficking of Women
5. Acid Attack
6. Sexual Harassment
7. Domestic Violence
8. Honour Killing

Study Area:

The South Solapur taluka is one of the most important taluka in Solapur district. The South Solapur taluka is located between 17° 21'0'' North latitudes and 17° 47'40'' North latitudes and 75° 34'0'' East longitudes and 76° 12'0'' East longitudes. The average height of South Solapur taluka from Mean Sea Level (MSL) varies from 500 meter to 600 meter. The South Solapur taluka has an irregular shape. The geographical area of South Solapur taluka is 1195 Sq.Km.

Objective:

The present study has following specific objective.

1. To study types of women crimes in study region.
2. To analyze women crime in study region.

LOCATION MAP OF SOUTH SOLAPUR TALUKA

Fig. No. 1

Data Collection and Methodology:

The proposed research paper based on secondary data. The secondary data is collected from District Gazetteers, Socio-Economic Review of Solapur district, Maharashtra Police crime report. The data processed and analyzed by using different cartographic techniques, statistical and quantitative techniques, etc.

Interpretation:

Women constitute half of the world population, due to differences in gender-wise as well as bias, women have been a victim of violence and exploitation by the so-called patriarchal society. In India, Women have been

exploited since the time immemorial -Socially, economically, Physically, Psychologically and Sexually too, by tradition-bound society.

The major crimes against women were rape; homicide for dowry, dowry deaths or their attempts; torture- both mental and physical; assault on women with intent to outrage her modesty; kidnapping and abduction; and cases under Dowry Prohibition Act where maximum number of cases were reported and there has been significant increase during 2015-2019 in the South Solapur taluka of Solapur district.

Following table shows the classification of women crime in South Solapur taluka of Solapur district.

Table No. 1. Classification of Women crimes in South Solapur taluka of Solapur district.

Sr. No.	Name of Crime	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
1	Rape	12	17	24	28	30
2	Dowry Death	27	32	40	43	47
3	Kidnapping	09	13	15	18	21
4	Trafficking of Women	05	11	15	19	23
5	Acid Attack	02	04	07	09	09
6	Sexual Harassment	26	32	37	40	43
7	Domestic Violence	45	56	59	63	66
8	Honour Killing	05	07	07	09	11

Source: Data complied by researcher.

Fig. No. 2

The table no.1 and fig. no. 2 shows the classification in South Solapur taluka of Solapur district. The women crime shows the numbers of crimes increase from 2015 to 2019 years. The Rape, Dowry death, Kidnapping, Trafficking of women, Acid attack, Sexual harassment, Domestic violence and Honour killing crimes shows the numbers of crimes against women increases. The data shows the every crime numbers from 2015 to 2019 the numbers are doubled which means the women crimes increases doubled in five years.

Conclusion:

Violence and crime against women is a social problem which is linked to gender inequality and violates the right of women to live without fear with freedom and dignity. The number of serious crimes against women such Rape, homicide for dowry, dowry deaths or their attempts, torture- both mental and physical,

assault on women with intent to outrage her modesty, kidnapping and abduction and cases under Dowry Prohibition Act have increased considerably. Despite high incidence of crime, the State Government has not taken effective steps to significantly strengthen its police force as the actual police manpower per one lakh population in the State is amongst the lowest in the country. Incidence of crime against women have been increasing consistently during last five years. The data shows the every crime numbers from 2015 to 2019 the numbers are doubled which means the women crimes increases doubled in five years.

References:

1. Ahuja. Ram. (1987): "Crime Against Women", Jaipur. India: Rawat Publications
2. Anita Parmar (2016): Crime against Women in India: Laws and Provisions, Journal Global Values Vol. - VII, No. 2 pp-

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3. Bhatnagar R.R. (1990): “Crime in India: Problems and Policy” Ashiah Publishing House, New Delhi.
4. Doyel, Mukhopadhyay (1999):” Geography of Urban Crime Against Women: comparative study of Calcutta and Toronto”, Thesis, Jawaharlal Nehru University, New Delhi.
5. Kumari, Radha. (1993): “Crime Against Women — Role of NGOa”, in O.C. Sharma(eds), Crime Against Women, Aahish Publishing House, N. Delhi. pp 145-149.
6. Maharashtra Police Crime reports 2015-2019.
7. Nayar B R. (1975): Violence and Crime in India A Quantitative study, Macmillan, Delhi.
8. S. Carlson, E. (1987): “Wife bartering: A Social Deviance Analysis”, in Figueira, J. Mcdonough and Sarri, R. (eda.), “The Trapped Women”, Sage, London. pp 172-196.
9. Socio-Economic review of Solapur district 2015-16-17-18-19.